

Midline Durotomy for Large Chiari Decompressions: A Technical Nuance in Skull Base Surgery

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INTRODUCTION

Large Chiari malformations usually require a conventional “Y-shaped” durotomy and C1 laminectomy with or without duraplasty. We have employed a midline durotomy approach, with tonsillar reduction and describe our experience.

METHODS

A consecutive series of patients undergoing a large Chiari decompression were prospectively followed at a single institution performed by a single surgeon over 1 year. The surgical technique is enabled by using the microscope at high magnification (working in a deep, narrow corridor).

Surgical Technique/Nuances

Prone Position
 Pins- optional
 Monitoring- Optional
 Small skin incision, 2-3cm
 Midline Durotomy
 Assess MRI for large midline occipital sinus
 Tonsillar reduction with bipolar & ultrasonic aspiration
 PICA- tonsillomedullary portion exposure
 Magendie and Obex exposure
 Patient bed angulated up to 30 degrees to facilitate tonsillar reduction

Some Disadvantages

-Very narrow operating corridor
 -injury to PICA or brainstem
 -Inadvertent occipital sinus injury

RESULTS

Table 1: Patient Demographics	N=9
Gender: M: F	3:6
Age at surgery/ yrs (Mean \pm SD)	7.8 \pm 4.5
Range	2-15

Table 2: Presenting Symptoms/Findings (%)	N=9
Headaches	55.6
Syrinx	33.3
Nausea/vomiting	22.2
Neck/back Pain	44.4
Scoliosis	11.1
Numbness/tingling	33.3
Average Tonsillar Herniation (mm)	13.4 \pm 4.3

Table 3: Perioperative Data	N=9
C1 Laminectomy (%)	55.6
Pin Cranial Fixation (%)	22.2
Dural Graft for Closure (%)	33.3
Surgery Duration (mins)	189.9 \pm 29.6
Estimated Blood Loss (mL)	32.1 \pm 22.0
Length of Stay (d)	4.3 \pm 3

CONCLUSIONS

A midline dural opening with or without C1 laminectomy can be safely performed in large Chiari malformations with good results. The complication rate of this technique falls within reported percentages of 4-40% complication rates.¹⁻⁷ The limited dural opening allows adequate tonsillar decompression, despite the narrow surgical window. A C1 laminectomy is not always necessary, even if the tonsils are located dorsal to the posterior arch of C1. C1 laminectomy was performed in all patients with syrinx. The tonsillo-medullary portion of the PICA is the landmark used to delineate adequate tonsillar reduction.

The microscope is utilized at a very high magnification and the patient position angled to facilitate lateral tonsillar reduction. The tonsils behind C1 can be debulked and delivered superiorly with microsurgical separation of arachnoid from the PICA during this maneuver.

Figure 1: Preoperative sagittal T2 MRI

Figure 2: Postoperative sagittal T2 MRI

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